

CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGIC SPECIFICITIES OF OUT-OF-HOSPITAL PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN AND SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. *Community-acquired pneumonia is one of the most common causes of morbidity in children and adolescents. In recent years, there has been an increasing tendency towards hypo- and overdiagnosis of the disease, as well as the formation of severe and complicated forms leading to death. We conducted a study of 960 case histories, among which 100 case histories of patients with community-acquired pneumonia were selected and patient management protocols were studied, which allowed us to identify seasonal fluctuations in the incidence of pneumonia in children and adolescents, the frequency of occurrence and clinical features of pneumonia.*

Keywords: *children, community-acquired pneumonia, diagnosis, treatment*

Аннотация. *Внебольничная пневмония является одной из наиболее распространенных причин заболеваемости детей и подростков. В последние годы наблюдается все большая тенденция к гипо- и гипердиагностике заболевания, а также к формированию тяжелых и осложненных форм, приводящих к летальному исходу. Мы провели исследование 960 историй болезни, среди которых было отобрано 100 историй болезни пациентов с внебольничной пневмонией и изучены протоколы ведения пациентов, что позволило нам выявить сезонные колебания заболеваемости пневмонией у детей и подростков, частоту возникновения и клинические особенности пневмонии.*

Ключевые слова: *дети, внебольничная пневмония, диагностика, лечение.*

Introduction

In the structure of pediatric morbidity pathology of the respiratory system steadily occupies the leading place. In particular, the incidence of community-acquired pneumonia in the regions ranges from 5 to 17 cases per 1000 children per year [1,7]. With age the incidence decreases 3-6 times, in school and adolescence about 13 cases per 1000 children per year are registered [2,8]. The high prevalence of pneumonia due to the duration of the disease and the formation of unfavorable variants of course and lethality can cause significant economic damage to society, determining the medical and social significance.

Despite the existing clear clinical and instrumental criteria for the diagnosis of out-of-hospital pneumonia in the pediatric population, the relevance of this topic remains. There is often a tendency to hypo- and hyperdiagnosis of the disease, as well as the formation of severe and complicated forms, annually recorded fatal cases. Given the relevance of this problem, we studied the clinical features of community-acquired pneumonia in children and adolescents who were treated in the pediatric pulmonology department of RChMMC Andijan.

We conducted a study of 960 case histories, among which 100 case histories of patients with out-of-hospital pneumonia were selected and the protocols of patient management were studied, which allowed us to identify clinical and epidemiologic features of pneumonia.

The aim of the study was to analyze the peculiarities of clinical symptoms and the course of acute pneumonia.

Materials and methods of the study. We analyzed 960 case histories of children who were hospitalized and underwent inpatient treatment at the pediatric pulmonology department of RChMMC Andijan for 2022-2023. Among them, 100 case histories of patients (41 boys and 39 girls) with pneumonia were selected and protocols of management of these patients were studied. The diagnosis of pneumonia was based on a careful analysis of anamnestic data of children, clinical manifestations of the disease, results of common laboratory tests and radiography data of their chest organs. Statistical processing was performed using the Excel 7.0 analysis package. Descriptive statistics of qualitative parameters is presented in the form of frequencies (abs., percentages).

Results and their discussion. During the analysis of 960 medical records of children, acute out-of-hospital pneumonia was detected in 100 children aged from 2 months to 17 years, including 61 boys and 39 girls. The predominant age group was 3-7 years old - 30.7% (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Pneumonias in children of different age groups

On admission to the emergency room, all patients (and/or their parents) complained of elevated body temperature (in most cases 90.6%, within febrile (38.1-39.0°C) and high febrile (39.1-40.0°C) figures. Patients also noted cough: more often sporadic character 81,3%, with difficult to separate sputum 65,3%. Runny nose was noted in 58.6% of children, of which 92.1% had serous nasal discharge and 7.9% had serous-purulent or purulent discharge. Increased frequency of respiratory movements was noted in all children.

Seasonal fluctuations in morbidity were observed during the calendar year, with the most frequent hospitalizations occurring in December and November (36 and 24 clinical cases, respectively) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Frequency of distribution of pneumonia cases in children depending on the time of year

The study of the medical history revealed that the duration of the disease up to the moment of hospitalization was 1-3 days in 30.0% of patients, 4-7 days - in 44.0% and more than 7 days - in 26.0%. 18.6% of patients had concomitant diseases that aggravated the course of the main disease (bronchial asthma, hypochromic anemia, herpetic infection, lymphatic hypoplastic constitutional anomaly, bilateral maxillary sinusitis, coarctation of the aorta, thymomegaly, functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, drug allergies).

Analysis of the results of the objective status of patients revealed dyspnea in all children.

At chest percussion over the lung surface, a blunted percussion sound was more often detected - 63.3%, rather than pulmonary 8.0% or boxy 28.7%. Auscultatively on the background of stiff breathing 82,6% dry wheezes were heard in 41,3%, moist wheezes - in 46,2%.

The standard of diagnostics of out-of-hospital pneumonia includes a number of laboratory-instrumental investigations [4,5]. In patients with pneumonia, the changes in peripheral blood were reduced to an increase in COE and a shift in the leukocytic formula. An increased number of leukocytes was detected in 44.6%, physiological - in 54.6% and decreased - in 0.8%. At the same time there was an increased relative content of neutrophils and correspondingly - decreased lymphocytes in 50,7%, neutropenia and lymphocytosis - in 39,3%, no changes - in 10,0%.

According to the data of radiographic lung examination, 70.6% of patients had right-sided and 26.0% had left-sided changes in the form of lung pattern enhancement with perivascular and peribronchial infiltration (23.1% and 30.7%, respectively), with segmental and/or polisegmental infiltration (35.4% and 32.9%, respectively), with lobular infiltration (41.5% and 36.4%, respectively). Bilateral root pneumonia was found in 5 (3.4%) patients of preschool age.

All patients were treated with etiotropic, pathogenetic and symptomatic therapy according to the standards of medical care. In pneumonia, empirical antibacterial therapy should be administered as early as possible, because the occurrence of complications and the risk of mortality increase due to the later administration of antibiotics [2,4,5,6].

Among antibacterial agents, III generation cephalosporins (Cefotaxime - 26.3%, Ceftazidime - 14.1%, Ceftriaxone - 12.2%, Cefixime - 2.3%), IV generation (Cefepime - 11, 3%) and I generation (Cefazolin - 0.6%), macrolides (Azithromycin - 14.3%), carbapenems (Meropenem - 10.3%), aminoglycosides (Gentamicin - 3.5%), protected penicillins (Broadsef - 5.1%) (Fig. 3)

Figure 3. Spectrum of antibiotic therapy in the treatment of pneumonia in children and adolescents (%)

In 28.0% of patients there were complications: respiratory failure - 19.3%, bronchoobstructive syndrome - 7.3%, toxicosis and hyperthermic syndrome - 0.6% each. In this connection, according to the protocol for the treatment of children with community-acquired pneumonia, inhaled corticosteroids were administered, and some patients were prescribed diuretics, methylxanthines, and bronchodilators in case of bronchospasm. Timely adequate therapy allows stabilizing the condition of children and discharging them under the supervision of a pediatrician, pulmonologist and other specialists.

Thus, our study allowed us to draw the following conclusions: 1.

1. Diseases of the respiratory system are a frequent pathology in children and adolescents. Out-of-hospital pneumonia accounts for 5.1% of all patients hospitalized in the pediatric therapeutic department in 2022-2023;

2. There were no gender differences among patients (61 boys (61.0%) and 39 girls (39.0%);

3. Comparative analysis of the data obtained in different age groups allowed to establish that pneumonias occurred more often at the age of 3 to 7 years - 30.7%;

4. Among the complaints, children and/or parents noted increased body temperature (90.6%, sporadic cough 81.3%, runny nose 58.6% with serous nasal discharge(81.3%.

5. Seasonal fluctuations in the incidence of out-of-hospital pneumonia in children and adolescents have been revealed, with the greatest rise in November and December;

6. Only 30.0% of patients are hospitalized on the 1st-3rd day after the first symptoms appear.

7. Bronchial asthma, hypochromic anemia, herpetic infection, bilateral maxillary sinusitis prevailed in the structure of concomitant diseases aggravating the course of pneumonia.

8. The results of objective examination revealed dyspnea (100.0%), at percussion - blunted 63.3%, pulmonary 8.0% or boxy 28.7% percussion sound, auscultation - hard breathing 82.6% with dry 41.3% or moist 46.2% rales.

9. Peripheral blood changes in most cases were reduced to an increase in COE and leukocytosis 44.6%. Relative increase in neutrophil count and decrease in lymphocyte count 50.7%, less frequently neutropenia and lymphocytosis 39.3% and no changes 10.0% were also detected.

10. In 70.6% of cases right-sided localization of the process was noted, in 26.0% - left-sided and 3.4% - bilateral according to the radiological study. More often there was lobular infiltration (41.5% on the right and 36.4% on the left) than segmental and/or polysegmental (35.4% and 32.9%, respectively) and peribronchial (23.1% and 30.7%, respectively).

11. All patients were treated with etiotropic, pathogenetic and symptomatic therapy according to the standards of medical care. III generation cephalosporins were used more often as etiotropic treatment 54.9%. Cefotaxime is the undisputed leader in terms of consumption.

Thus, timely assessment of the condition of children, laboratory and instrumental studies and rational treatment allow to stabilize the patient's condition and prevent the development of complications and the risk of mortality. The results of the study should be taken into account when examining and prescribing complex and rational treatment.

REFERENCES

1. Ganiev A.G. Analysis of the course of community-acquired pneumonia in children in Andijan International scientific journal "News of Education: research in the XXI century" №. 15(100), part 2 November, 2023. Articles 109-111.
1. Ganiev A.G., Arifkhodzhaev A.T. Clinical and etiological characteristics of out-of-hospital acute pneumonia in children under one year of age and their treatment Journal of innovations in scientific and educational research volume №6. 5.pp. 875-881
2. Geppe N.A., Volkov I.K. Prospects of development and problems of pediatric pulmonology in Russia // Pulmonology. 2007. №. 4. pp. 5-6.
3. Grigoriev K.I. Modern view of pneumonia in children and approaches to its treatment and prevention // Medical care. 2005. №. 2. pp. 3-9.
4. Evdokimova D.V., Ulanova A.V. Investigation of the features of community-acquired pneumonia in children and adolescents. Materials of the 52nd annual All-Russian Conference of students and Young Scientists "Actual problems of theoretical, experimental, clinical medicine and pharmacy", dedicated to the sacred 90th anniversary of the doctor.
5. Nazarov K.D., Ganiev A.G. Community-acquired pneumonia in children: clinical, laboratory and etiological features Journal of hepato-gastroenterology research journal of hepato-gastroenterology research. Special edition. Toshkent 2023 St:78-84
6. Zakirov I.I., Safina A.I. Criteria for diagnosis and treatment of community-acquired pneumonia in children // Practical medicine. 2012. №. 7. pp. 32-37.
7. Acute respiratory diseases in children: treatment and prevention. Scientific and practical program of the Union of Pediatricians of Russia. Moscow: International Foundation for Maternal and Child Health, 2002. 69 p.